

DESCRIPTION OF KOKAN KHANATE IN THE TRAVELOGUE OF TRAVELER MIR IZZATULLO.

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes diplomatic relations sent to Central Asia from the British Empire on the basis of archival sources and scientific literature in various countries.

Since it is impossible to defeat a nation that knows its history and attains spiritual strength from it, we need to reinstate our fair history, furnish our people and supply it once again has become the spiritual weapon of our historians, nowadays.

Many European scientists and tourists have scientifically studied Central Asia in different countries. But in the middle of the 19th century, there are very few tourists who traveled to the region of 3 khanates, whose various aspects and characteristics of life were not well known to Europeans. One such tourist is Mir Izzatullo, who wrote down information about his trip in 1812 to the Khanate of Kokan. He visited on the assignment of William Moorcroft, a famous figure of the British colony in India (East India). The reason for this was the increasing interest of British businessmen in establishing trade and economic relations with the then little-explored countries in the north of the Hindikush (India).

There is almost no biographical information about Mir Izzatullo's life. It is known that he belonged to the Muslim population of India and served in the British army.

His work is written in Persian language, usually written in the form of pioneering notes of oriental authors. The information presented in it (Kokan-Samarkand-Bukhara directions in the part of Central Asia presented here) includes some interesting and important historical ethnographic and historical geographical information of the beginning of the 19th century.

The work on the details of Mir Izzatullo's journey was translated into French by G.Claprot in 1826, P. D. Henderson in Calcutta in 1872 in English, its Russian text was first published in 1956.

In his travelogue, important information about the connecting roads of the cities Kashkar, Kokan, Samarkand, the people living there, their settlements, lifestyle, rulers and their deputies were recorded.

In particular, the thirty-fourth chapter is called " The Road from Koshkar to Kokan ", and in it we find the following information: " Three hours West of Osh, closer to the north (the first city

is Fergana, multi-ethnic and well-supplied with waterways). From these famous places, the Fergana region begins. The road is open (good), passed through the plain. On the way, there are many stations of the Kyrgyz subordinate to Osh (places where emissaries and caravans stop).

The following information is given about the lifestyle of the inhabitants living between Urgantov, Kashkar and Kurashim live independently from Kashkar. They bring fuel and coal to this city for sale. These Kyrgyz do not need to obtain a Chinese passport when leaving the territory of Koshkar, they can move freely through these areas and leave them at will. All of them are subservient to Chinese authorities.

There are also tribes living between Kurashim and Osh, who live under the authority of the Kokan Khanate. Most of them are rich stockmen and have their own large number of horses and sheep".

Dwelling on the measures taken to ensure safety on the caravan routes in the Kokan Khanate: " During the time of Kokan khan Norbotabi, there were robberies along the main road where the caravan roads passed, but his successor, his son Olimkhan, took strict measures against robbers and since then it was completely safe ".

He also spoke about the historical and holy shrines in the Kokan Khanate: " (They say) The throne of Osh is known as Suleiman (the capital of Solomon). The city is provided with waterways. The governor of this city is appointed by the Kokan Khan, and Muhammad Yor, known as Makhdum, rules. Here they showed the tomb of Osaf Berk, the minister of the Prophet Suleiman. I visited it and it looks very impressive. It is said that the throne of Suleiman descended from the sky on the hill, and his palace was built in the form of a single dome. Pilgrims of different nationalities from the surrounding countries come here to visit the tomb of the Prophet Suleiman in the spring months. This holy shrine is located West of Osh. Pilgrims bring various products to sell and barter here. The market is held every Tuesday of the week.

In spring, there are many small mosquitoes (flies) here. During the hot summer, the people living here sleep on raised four-sided daises (mosquito net) covered with cloth".

In the travelogue, the cities of the Kokan Khanate are described as follows:" Two days' journey north-west of Osh is the city of Namangan, famous for its sweet fruits. Andijan, the former capital of Fergana (which has now lost its importance), is three days' journey from Osh, a little further north in the direction. Once upon a time Umarshaikh Mirza, the father of Babur Mirza, who ruled India, had his residence in this city. However, Andijan is also famous at the same time (19th century)".

Chapter 36 of the travelogue describes the villages on the way to the city of Kokan, their inhabitants, and their activities. For example: " Mingtepa is a three hour drive to the west. Turkic and Kipchak tribes live in vast mountainous areas and pastures around the village. Here, they graze their herds in spring and summer, 10-12000 families are united both tribes and live a prosperous life. The men are handsome, good-looking, well-dressed and have a good military education, while the Kyrgyz, on the other hand, are mostly poor, ugly and lack military skills ".

Mir Izzatullo cites the map of cities and villages in the direction leading to the city of Kokan, the center of the Khanate, as follows:

"37. The inn (given as Mrs. Luly's Millhead in the English edition) is three hours' drive

to the west. One day's journey north of this village is the city of Andijan. Also, in the north of the village is called Kubo. One farsakh from it, there are stations (yom) of Kyrgyz and Kalmyks, whose inhabitants are considered the last Muslims in this direction.

38. The bridge (given as Korchok in the English edition) is five hours to the west and north. There is a village on the road, near which the waterways are crossed by a bridge.

39. Margilon - six hours to the west, to the north. This vast city overlooks the territory of Fergana. Here is the famous tomb of Iskander, who is compared to Alexander the Great. Margilon is a pleasant city with friendly people. The city is ruled by the son of Kokan Khan.

Large quantities of silk fabrics are produced here, as well as woollen fabrics for scarves. It is called Kursi in Persian and Tibet in Turkish. Shawls are also made in Margilon, but they are lower quality than those woven in Kashmir.

The city is surrounded by an earthen wall, but it is currently in a dilapidated state. A large and strong tower was built in the center of the city.

41. Karakhitai - four hours to west. The population is mainly Muslim. Although we were travelling across country from the desert, we saw populated villages on our left. Two roads lead from Margilon to Kokan: one crosses the country, the other passes through the territory of cities and villages.

42. Kokan - about eight hours to the west, slightly north. It is also written Kokan (Khokan). This spacious and beautiful city is not surrounded by defensive walls. It is associated with the period when Norbotabi founded it, it was previously considered a small village. River tributaries run through every street of this city. Its current ruler is Umarchan.

Tourist Mir Izzatullo touched on the political and social situation in Kokan and covered the following events in his diary: "Two years ago, in 1228, during the reign of his (Umarchan's) elder brother Olimkhan's tyranny and increased persecution aroused discontent from the people of the entire country. Especially, in his army when the protest escalated and the khan came to Tashkent, they (the army), returned to Kokan and raised his brother Umarchan as khan. Olimkhan, who was coming to suppress the unrest in Kokan, was killed on the way before he could enter the city. Olimkhan and Umarchan were the children of Norbotabi.

Mir Izzatullo also spoke about the military situation of the Kokan Khanate: "The army of the Kokan khan shows that it consists of 10,000 horsemen. They will receive land and property in exchange for military service. This army can withstand two months during military mobilization. The part called ulus or mirshabs consists of 30,000 people and is not provided with any funds from the state. They are separated peasants who are called from their farms for one month a year. The Kyrgyz, Turks, Kipchaks and Kazakh nations are subordinate to the Kokan Khanate. Most of the Khanate's troops are armed with bows and some of them have rifles. The above-mentioned cities of Osh, Namangan, Koson and Chust, and the cities of Andijan, Margilon, Konibodom, Isfarak and Khojand, each of which is two days' distance from Namangan, are subject to the Kokan Khanate.

Except for Chust and Namangan, all these cities are located on the left bank of Syr Darya (Sayhun or Okuz). On the right banks of Syr Darya are the Andijan mountains, covered with grasses and shrubs, and the cities of Shuhrukhiya, Tashkent, Sayram, Kalai Turkistan are also in this direction. The region where the city of Tashkent is located which is known as Turkistan. Its ancient name is Shosh. It is surrounded by a wide and large plain, through

which the Chirchik river flows. To the north of the Andijan mountains is a large region bordering the territory of Russia, the population of which consists mainly Kazaks and Karakalpaks.

The capital of the khans of this country is the city of Bulgar or Kazan, and it is subject to the Russian Empire. This plain borders the Black Sea to the west and China to east.

Touching on the monetary reform carried out in the Kokan Khanate: "Umarkhan minted his own coins in Kokan. 1 coin is equal to 16 money (money is about 2 miskels). One Bukhara gold coin is worth 150 local chaka in Kokan. The local coin is a copper chaka, covered with silver".

The following information is provided about the relations between Kokan and Bukhara: "From the outside, Kokan and Bukhara seem to be in a friendly relationship. Kokan is a fully independent state from the Bukhara Emirate. Umarkhan set an army to Bukhara and put it in a difficult situation".

Regarding the spoken language of Kokan residents: "The spoken language of local residents is Turkish, but there are some people who understand Persian".

The following information is also found in the travelogue about some of the officials in the Kokan Khanate: "Mirza Yusuf Khojandi is an important official under the emir, and in fact he is the prime minister followed by Mir Ismatullah. Mir Yusuf Khojandi showed kindness towards me and tried to persuade me to stay in Kokan. He offered the position of the head of the Kokan madrasa".

In conclusion, it can be said that Mir Izzatullo's travel diaries to the Kokan Khanate are a valuable historical and geographical source for the history of the nations of Central Asia in the 19th century. Its value lies in the fact that the populace of Europe get to know the population, lifestyle and socio-political history of the Kokan Khanate. After the publication of Mir Izzatullo's diaries, European inhabitants gained a certain idea about the territory and population of Central Asia expanded. In addition, the map made by the tourist served as a basis for European tourists, soldiers and all visitors to Central Asia in later times.

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